

THE CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF PROFESSIONAL STANDARD IMPLEMENTATION IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The theory represents a visual representation of the expected result as the first idea to express the practice. To ensure the viability of the proposed idea, step-by-step planning, determination and implementation of tasks aimed at continuous improvement in the process are important. The article analyzes the methodological basis of the "Professional Standard of General Secondary Education School Teacher" implemented in the republic today, as well as foreign and national pedagogic research on it.*

Keywords: *professional development, level, skill, assessment, knowledge, qualification, requirements, legal and regulatory documents.*

INTRODUCTION. Changes in society are setting new challenges not only for schools but also for teachers, who play an important role in the development of education, requiring a professional level. The main requirement is that the teacher's scientific outlook and thinking should strengthen his professional practice and his efforts should ensure the quality of education. When analyzing education research, it was witnessed that there are many topics related to the professional development of teachers and teacher-student relations.

The scope of this theoretical research, which is presented, includes the concept of the expected qualification of a pedagogical worker and their lifelong professional development: the standard of the profession, its methodological foundations, a typology of advanced ideas, and an analysis. Self-assessment of a teacher or external assessment of his professional skills has always been difficult. In most cases, its capabilities to support and analyze development needs are insufficient. However, in the development of school education, the need for specific professional qualifications and standards that meet the needs of individuals and institutions, the priorities of goals, has been confirmed by practice, and high hopes have been placed on the teacher's behavior.

ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL LITERATURE. The need for teachers to help their students become creative future specialists who can adapt to the demands and needs of the future society is emphasized in the report of the International Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [16]. Also, in several foreign studies:

- teacher's professional development and skills play an important role in the perspective of sustainable education [10; 12; 11];
- the use of professional standards to assess the knowledge, skills, competence and professionalism required of teachers is a way to ensure continuous professional development [18];
- the development of the concept of standards and at the same time the fact that evaluation criteria have clear descriptive qualities is a factor in ensuring the quality of teachers [17];

- professional standards are a means of raising the status of the teacher, the quality or level of the achieved achievement should be comparatively evaluated by established qualification requirements, and this gives confidence to the teacher [14];

- the professional standard plays an important role in evaluating the professional development of the teacher, while the existing certification provides him with the opportunity to be recognized [11].

There are also researches that the teacher's professional standard, first of all, leads to self-analysis and evaluation, and these cannot be imagined separately from each other. Another study stated that the purpose of the professional standard used in Estonia is to transform teachers into reflective practitioners and lifelong learners throughout their careers [13]. In essence, the ideas expressed in the research analyzed above serve to complement each other, and the conducted research has led to the improvement of the professional standard, as an object of research, it has a strong place in society.

On May 15, 2020, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 287 [4] "On measures to organize the activities of the national system of professional qualifications, knowledge and skills development in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted in our country. In the same year, this decision was adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 31, 2020 "On measures to fundamentally improve the skills assessment system and provide the labor market with qualified personnel" PQ-4939 [3] made more relevant. Based on the above legal and regulatory documents, the working group of the Abdulla Avloni Research Institute for Studying the Problems of Public Education and Determining its Prospects has developed the "Professional Standard of General Secondary Education School Teacher" [6]. However, the standard in practice has hardly been analyzed and rarely researched.

In particular, the researcher-scientist A.Ibragimov conducted research to study the knowledge of the theories and professional standards of university teachers being put into practice and their attitude towards their implementation, and in the experimental work comprehensively analyzed the opinions expressed by teachers [7; pp. 47-56]. Continuing his scientific research, a comparative analysis of the content of professional standards for pedagogues introduced in different countries emphasizes the presence of common approaches, structural similarities, and at the same time, parts that differ from each other. According to the comparative analysis of the standards of 7 countries (Australia, Canada, Chile, USA, England, Mexico and New Zealand) cited in the works of B.Pont, it was determined that they mainly consist of three components: the knowledge of the pedagogue, the activities he performs and having due values; and the contents of the components can be distinguished from each other or have different names in a separate table [8; p. 114]. In particular, based on the author's approach, he developed the draft of the professional standard of "Teacher of General Secondary Education School" [8; p. 292].

At the same time, the team of authors published a manual for teachers and methodologists entitled "Application of the professional Standard in the Work of a general secondary school teacher", which describes the structure of the professional standard, the social and detailed information on professional competencies, areas of professional standard and the requirement of its application. Regarding the social competencies and values of the teacher in the manual, "To ensure effective teaching, it is necessary for the teacher to have developed social competencies. These competencies guarantee his readiness for the demands and obligations of teaching in a constantly changing world" [9; p. 14]. Also, he grouped the main values important in the teacher's

professional activity into three areas: 1) focus on the student - respect for the personality, dignity and individuality of the student, activity by the best interests of the child, perception of the world from his point of view; 2) pedagogue as a person and a master of his profession - adherence to universal and professional principles, striving for quality, continuous improvement and direction, innovation, acceptance of changes and adaptation, analysis and introduction of various changes in professional practice, understanding and favoring fairness and impartiality; 3) pedagogue as a member of the school community - cooperation, joint solution of professional problems, responsibility and participation in the organizational development of the school. In general, it can be recognized that the requirements and labor tasks are covered more widely in this manual.

Professional standards are formed based on classification units and requirements that reflect the social order. Today, the countries of the world are creating national qualification frameworks based on the "International Standard Classification of Education" (ISCED - International Standard Classification of Education) [5]. This document overcomes the problematic situations that arise in the comparative assessment of achievements and the study of progress for international goals due to the diversity of national education systems and programs of different countries. ISCED was adopted at the 36th session of the General Conference of UNESCO in November 2011 to interpret the process and its important aspects in education systems at the global level, classify and compare internationally comparable data and a conceptual document for submission is considered.

This classification ensures the consistency of the concepts used in the national content of countries and covers education in its entirety. ISCED 2011 consists of three components: 1) internationally agreed rules and definitions; 2) classification systems; and 3) classification of national education programs according to ISCED and relevant qualifications in the countries of the world. It also includes 8 levels starting from 0:

- level 0 - early childhood education;
- level 1 - primary education;
- level 2 - basic secondary education;
- level 3 – complete secondary education;
- level 4– primary vocational education;
- level 5 – secondary special vocational education;
- level 6– bachelor's degree or equivalent education;
- level 7 – master's degree or equivalent education;
- level 8– doctorate or equivalent education.

ISCED levels are used to compare data and aid in their international interpretation. By linking the criteria for the classification of national curricula according to ISCED with the characteristics of curricula and related qualifications, it provides transparency in the process of coding national curricula and related qualifications into comparable categories for use in international statistics. In other words, it is recommended that every country that wants the personnel trained in the education system and the achievements achieved in it to be recognized in the international system, based on its national mentality, should develop its qualification frameworks and educational standards by the above levels.

The sphere of continuous professional development is in the constant focus of the President of our republic, Sh.Mirziyoev, as problems that need to be solved quickly to implement education and science, the state's youth policy, and the introduction of new, modern methods of education.

“...the professional level of pedagogues and teaching staff, their special knowledge. In this regard, creating an environment that actively supports the processes of education, issues of spiritual and educational maturity, and the formation of real values” [1; p. 284], it is also emphasized that "the development of school education must become a great national goal, a national movement for us" [2; p. 160]. To improve the fields of education and science in our country, to strengthen the respect for teachers and pedagogic staff in our society, to support the development of their professional skills, as well as to evaluate teachers with specific criteria, this Conceptual basis of organizing the activities of the national system of the Republic of Uzbekistan Cabinet of Ministers dated May 15, 2020 No. 287 "On measures to organize the activities of the national system for the development of professional qualifications, knowledge and skills in the Republic of Uzbekistan" found its full reflection in the decision [4].

RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS. Below, we will focus on the essence of the documents adopted by this decision, which played a leading role in the development of professional standards. With this decision: the National Qualifications Framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan (document 1) and the Regulation on the National System of Professional Qualifications, Knowledge and Skills Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan (document 2) are approved. In the "General Provisions" chapter of the 1st document, “The National Qualifications Framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the National Qualifications Framework) sectoral qualification frameworks, professional and educational standards, national and international recognition of qualifications at all levels of professional education It is the institutional component and basis of the national system of intersectoral and international skills development, which provides a single mechanism for it.” The essence of this definition is that the national qualifications framework is a tool for integrating the labor market and education; harmonizing the results of vocational training and the knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies obtained as a result of training, forming a strong system of interrelationship between such skills and needs, implementing the process of assessing the compatibility of the obtained results with the qualification requirements and professional standards, represents that it ensures the recognition of qualifications at national and international levels.

The tabular structure of the National Qualifications Framework, 8 qualification levels in accordance with the European Qualifications Framework and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", as well as the following ways to achieve the corresponding qualification levels and containing the indicators:

knowledge - that is, the volume and complexity of the information being used; innovativeness; expressed such characteristics as the ratio of theoretical and practical knowledge;

skills and abilities - the variability of performing professional tasks, the need to choose options for solving tasks and develop ways to do it; the uncertainty of the work situation and the impossibility of determining its development in advance;

competencies - activity under leadership; independent execution discipline; management activities; the scope of activity, that is, the scope of authority and responsibility, the consequences of a possible error in professional activity;

the ways of obtaining qualifications are represented by the levels of education established by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The specified 8 qualification levels reflect the indicators within the framework of international standards and imply adherence to the principles specified in the "Final Regulations" section.

The principle of continuity and consistency of the development of the levels of qualifications from the bottom up (that is, by the levels of qualifications for the teacher). For example, if the first level of knowledge (at least elementary education) is general knowledge in the field of work or study, as the level increases, the knowledge framework becomes more complex based on the principle of continuity and consistency of the development of skill levels from the bottom up, and each at one level, the classification of additional knowledge has entered, and at level 8, highly specialized knowledge in an advanced field of work or study and interdisciplinary is shown as a unit. In the same way, the ways of acquiring skills and abilities, competence and skills have also changed following the classification of knowledge in the construction.;

- transparency of the description of qualification levels for all users (transparency of the results expected from the teacher's pedagogical activity, openness in the evaluation of professional qualifications, knowledge and skills.);

- the compatibility of the hierarchy of qualification levels with the structure of the division of labor and the national education system (this principle is based on the National Qualification Framework for teachers and the assessment system based on it, which is primarily aimed at protecting the interest of the region, means compliance with the requirements established in society, and other aimed at ensuring communication with systems, expressing the suitability and compatibility of existing processes);

- World experience in developing the structure and content of the National Qualifications Framework (the National Qualifications Framework is based on the structures and content of the frameworks of the European Union countries, including ISCED - International Standards of Education, the Republic of Korea, the Russian Federation and other countries where such experience has been gathered).

Document 2 - The Regulation on the National System of Professional Qualifications, Knowledge and Skills Development (hereinafter referred to as the National Qualifications System) and the procedure for applying it, as well as the employment of the unemployed and unemployable population. It contains 14 chapters that determine the order of training, retraining and advanced training, and determine the importance of each sub-element in the process: An explanation of each concept used in the regulation, as well as the purpose, tasks, basic components of the National Qualifications System, the content of the professional standard, the procedure for its development, etc.

CONCLUSION. It can be concluded that the introduction of professional standards actualizes the necessity and need to radically change the external (educational environment, social order, management, etc.) and internal (pedagogue's personal, independent) relations to the teacher's activity. The introduction of professional standards into practice as a simple and effective tool creates an obligation to train, retrain, improve the qualifications of pedagogues, conduct attestation, improve continuous methodical service procedures, look at them from a different perspective, and make corrections. Also, the ability of the teacher to imagine the requirements for his pedagogical activity and his mission, moving on the "social elevator" on this basis, creates a constant motivation for self-professional development, strengthening his status, and full realization of his potential.

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